

DEVELOPMENTAL CHARACTERISTICS OF YOUTH SOCIALIZATION PROCESS.

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Abstract: The article presents theoretical analyzes of the role of education in the social development of young people, moral education, development of methods and forms of education of students in higher education.

Key words: Social development, education, upbringing, morals, manners, educational-ethical direction, method, form, research, family, higher educational institution, cultural relations, fragments of history.

We consider the concept of social development of youth as an objective and, at the same time, socially regulated process of interaction of irreversible social changes of the young generation in the process of formation of social production and social life as a subject. It is the goals and progress (regression) of society. One of the distinctive features of the sociological method of studying this process comes from the objectivity of the process of the development of young people as a social group, since not every change describes the development of young people, but only one change is taken into account. The unity of properties such as irreversibility and directionality.

If the irreversibility of social changes in the young generation characterizes the stability of the process and separates the development of youth from its functioning, then the direction of the changing characteristics of youth gives the character of internal interdependence to the development process.

The instability of certain positive social changes among young people, unpredictable, spontaneous events indicate that these changes have not yet become irreversible.

Mistakes in the choice of means and methods of implementing socio-economic changes in the country, the long-term neglect of many social factors in the development of society, the orientation of management to administrative-administrative methods affect the direction of youth policy. It did not show. It turned out that there is no clear concept of social development of modern youth, the individual, mainly administrative measures announced in many decisions were not interrelated, targeted. The development of development goals in youth education was carried out in isolation from the real social processes taking place in society and among young people.

As a result of the implemented reforms, the processes involving the modern young generation are more controversial. When it comes to renewing the social system with internal structural and functional changes, there is a difficult and laborious search for ways to achieve social progress corresponding to the current stage of development of Uzbek society. Therefore, in the most general form, the social development of young people means the quantitative and qualitative change of their social characteristics during the formation of young people as subjects of social reproduction [1].

The determination of this issue as an independent direction in the sociology of youth is due to the growing need for a systematic study of this social group, which is related to the consideration of social processes in the youth environment in dynamics, and youth themselves. development. At each stage of its development, society develops individual requirements for the young generation in the form of social norms, values, ethics, etc., and also creates various opportunities for the successful integration of young people into social structures. This is done through the state policy on youth. Therefore, there is a need to separately study the social mechanisms of interaction between society and youth, and to conduct scientific research of conceptual approaches to their social development. L. Rosenmayer emphasized that generations are social changes that determine the uniqueness of lifestyle and not vice versa. As J. Elil noted, every social event is an evolution. There are no "sudden events", there is constant change[2].

It should be taken into account that not every change characterizes the development of youth, only one is carried out in the unity of characteristics such as irreversibility and direction. Consciously developed social relations in modern societies form the basis of scientifically based regulation of this process. Noting this feature, we do not mean to manipulate young people, to have a voluntary influence on their fate, but to create the necessary conditions for socialization, to use the whole complex of regulation; describing educational practice.

For a long time, our social science mainly focused on social development by analyzing its natural changes. Fundamental development of this problem began ten years ago under the leadership of V. Chuprov of the Institute of Social Sciences of the USSR in the sector of social problems of youth and continued in the Center of Youth Sociology of the Institute of Social and Political Research. Russian Academy of Sciences. The works of V. Borovik, S. Bykova, D. Jumakuliyev, G. Juravlev, E. Igitkhanyan, I. Kazarinova, E. Katulsky, L. Koklyagina,

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At the same time, the social development of youth, which is an integral part of the general processes of reforming social relations, has a number of characteristics. These characteristics, first of all, arise from the objective essence of youth. The objective basis of the concept of "youth" is related to its unique place in the system of reproduction and development of society; that is, the activity and development of young people as a large social group reflects the formation of the subject of social production and social life.

In this social quality, young people are primarily characterized by social relations and social forms that systematically determine them to an independent (compared to others) socio-demographic group. Here, the specific social quality of youth is related to the specific role it occupies in the process of reproduction of the social structure and is determined by the ability of the young generation to reproduce the structure of social relations prevailing in its time. formation. In other words, we're talking about a guy's potentially significant powers.

At the current stage, the unique social quality of young people is determined not only by the ability of the young generation to inherit and reproduce the social structure of social relations that appeared during its formation, but also by the ability to participate in its active improvement and change.

Secondly, as an emerging subject of social production, young people express the personal and objective aspects of concrete historical existence with special meaning. This manifestation of the social quality of young people is related to the specific features of their social status and is determined by the features of the socialization process in certain social conditions.

The specific living conditions of young people determine the specific characteristics of young people's consciousness, the dialectical unity of its constituent elements constitutes the important motivating and motivating forces of young people. Within this unity, various conflicting decisions arise on the basis of youth issues.

The listed manifestations of the social quality of young people overlap each other in the process of development, complement each other externally and internally, determine its social essence, which is carried out through activity.

Thus, in the study of young people, the following relatively independent, but strongly interconnected components are considered: potentially important forces (personal potential); stimulating and social activity that is a way to realize important forces. Each of the listed components is essentially the basis for the social development of young people and is considered one of the areas of sociological research.

Potential social forces determine the personal capabilities (potential) of the young generation, that is, its ability to become a subject of social production and social life in the process of development. Each new generation has the ability to consume productively, and "individual and personal consumption capacity becomes a productive force, just as it ensures the development of the vital forces of man"⁴. Their role in the two-way direction of abilities is great. emerging as a potentially important force of youth.

The social nature of youth. In sociology, the issue of abilities is poorly developed. Therefore, sociological research of this category, especially its empirical interpretation, seems relevant. Here, the object of analysis is not a person and his individual inclinations, but rather a certain result of the personal capabilities of individual groups of young people, which allows us to talk about the personal potential of the group, not the total (sum) of individual abilities, stratum, generation. based on the prevalence of this trait in the population.

For this purpose, the typology of abilities in psychology (intellectual, emotional, communicative, practical) is adapted to the objectives of sociological research.

In the problems of social development of young people, the motivational sphere of consciousness is also the most important characteristic of this socio-demographic group.

From an individual psychological point of view, such a view of the motivational sphere can be explained by its connection with the orientation of the individual. "Orientation can be evaluated as a relationship between what a person receives and receives from society (meaning material and spiritual values) and what it gives him and contributes to his development."⁵ In the sociological context, this approach is based on consideration. in the system of reproduction and development of society, youth are called to perform a specific important task. This function is carried out through reproductive and innovative activity.

Intervening in social relations, young people change them and improve themselves under the influence of changed conditions. The negative influence of

conditions and relationships on the social activities and activities of young people occurs indirectly through their consciousness, in the form of a certain structure of needs, interests and values. Thus, the motivational sphere of youth consciousness is a complex systematic formation, which is a product of the immediate conditions of the young generation's life in the process of its formation as a subject of social production and community life. This approach provides a complete analysis of the motivational field, which allows us to have an idea of motivation as a direction of consciousness, distinguishing it from the motivation of specific types of activities or specific actions.

The main motivational relations of the person are formed in the process of socialization of young people. But socialization itself does not come from imitation of social roles, but includes "the process of active reproduction of the system of social relations through the active activity of the individual, active inclusion in the environment."⁶ Therefore, cognitive and transformative stages differs in socialization.

In the process of socialization, young people not only learn and assimilate the social norms and cultural values of society, but also transform them into their own values, interests and needs. If the dominant method of activity for the cognitive stage of socialization is imitation, for the transformational stage it is innovation. Accordingly, the result of socialization can be a stereotypical-personal (conservative) or active-personal (productive) stage of consciousness and behavior.

Activity in the internalization of social experience is an important condition of social creativity of young people, the key to the innovative process. However, orientation towards creative and transformative activities is not a sign of development in itself, even in the motivational sphere of young people. Development refers to the directed process of social change. Only the changes that occur in the mind of young people during the socialization process can reflect their ontogenetic development process. In other words, the development of young people in ontogenesis is considered as a transition from stereotypical-personal consciousness to an active-personal type of consciousness.

Regarding the development of youth as an intergenerational process in phylogeny, here we also encounter the relationship between continuity and innovation. Only the direction of this process is determined by the criteria of society's development, if continuity from a social point of view is understood as a simple reproduction of the existing system of social relations by the younger generation, it is manifested in the change of its social innovation. these

relationships, during these relationships, a new social quality is formed. The unity of these two aspects of youth social development reflects the dialectic of the transition from simple to extended social reproduction. Therefore, the direction of changes in the motivational sphere of consciousness is an important feature of the social development of young people.

The process of social reproduction is accompanied by a qualitative change in the social position (status) of the young generation. This is reflected in the positive changes in the social structure of young people and their social identification in the process of their inclusion in different levels of social communities.

Identity of youth as a social group. The specific characteristics of the social structure of the younger generation (due to the transition period, as well as the changes taking place in society itself) include:

firstly, the presence of a large number of young people (students) who do not have their own social status in the full sense of the word and are characterized by their past social status - the social status of their parents' family. according to his future status in relation to professional training;

secondly, the social characteristics of different categories of young people are determined not only by their official affiliation to different structures of society, but also by their direct participation in mass movements. Socio-cultural models of the youth mass (informal, movement, cohort, etc.) formed in this way differ significantly.

Understanding the nature of qualitative changes in the important characteristics of young people is directly related to the source of its development, that is, the nature of the objective contradictions that are the basis for the development of this socio-demographic group. Youth is not a self-developing system. Being a part of society, he enters into all the diversity of his connections and relationships. At the same time, it has its own social functions - reproductive, translational and innovative. Defining youth as a relatively independent social group is primarily related to reproductive function.

References:

- 1 Подробнее см.: Ч у про в В. И. Развитие молодежи: концептуализация понятия// Молодежь России: социальное развитие/ Отв. ред. Н.С.Слепцов. М., 1992. С. 6-22.
- 2 Подробнее см.: Иконников а С.Н. Молодежь: социологический и социально-психологический анализ. Л., 1974.

3 Чупров В. И. Теоретические и прикладные проблемы социального развития молодежи. Диссертация в форме научного доклада на соискание учен. степ. докт. социол. наук. М., 1994. С. 6-10.

4. Djalolovich, R. J. (2023). Nikoh-oila munosabatlari Shakllanishining ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari. Barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy Jurnali, 3(3), 473-477.

5. Ramazonov, J., & Xomidov, M. (2024). MILLIY QADRIYATLAR ASOSIDA SHAXS MA'NAVIY KAMOLOTI SHAKLLANISHINING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 3(1), 200-202.

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